

Novel Features in Oxidation of Hydrocarbons by V^v-Salt Effects

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Salt effects on the rate of oxidation of toluenes by V^v have been investigated. The rate depends on the character and concentration only of the cations of the added salt, not on the ionic strength. The relative order of cations is Mg > Cr > NH₄ > UO₂ > Na ≈ Co ≈ Mn > Al. The Olson-Simonson effect is quite compatible with ion-dipole reactions.

We have recently reported our results on the oxidation of toluenes and substituted toluenes by V^v and Ce.IV^{1,2,3}. In this communication the effect of various salts on the oxidation of hydrocarbons by V^v is reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : All compounds used were AR grade.

All the inorganic compounds (reagent grade) were converted to the anhydrous forms before preparing solutions.

Rate measurements : Flasks containing two stock solutions were allowed to come to bath temperature. Insulated pipettes maintained at bath temperature were used to remove and transfer 50 ml aliquots to reaction flask, which was painted black to prevent exposure to light and was fitted with narrow neck which just admitted the pipette. At intervals of time a 5 ml sample of the reaction mixture was withdrawn, discharged into 10 ml of cold ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and immediately titrated with standard potassium dichromate solution using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as indicator.

The temperature fluctuations of the thermostat were ±0.01.

All the experiments have been carried out in duplicate and the velocity constants were reproducible to within 3%.

1. P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and Subas C. Pati, *Israel Journal of Chemistry*, 1969, 7, 427.
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RESULTS

The rate constants with various salts are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Acidity—8.1 <i>N</i> H ₂ SO ₄		Substrate—Toluene	
Solvent Composition (% v/v) HOAc—H ₂ O 50–50		Temp. 60°.	
Conc. of Ammonium Acetate	10 ³ <i>k</i> ₂ l moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	Conc. of Ammonium Sulphate	10 ³ <i>k</i> ₂ l moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
.00 <i>M</i>	3.343	.00 <i>M</i>	3.343
.01 <i>M</i>	3.846	.01 <i>M</i>	4.074
.025 <i>M</i>	5.00	.025 <i>M</i>	5.610
.05 <i>M</i>	7.194	.04 <i>M</i>	7.499
.075 <i>M</i>	10.0	.05 <i>M</i>	9.219
		.075 <i>M</i>	12.48

TABLE II

Acidity—8.1 <i>N</i> (H ₂ SO ₄)		Substrate : Toluene	
Solvent Composition (% v/v) HOAc—H ₂ O 50–50		Temp. 60°	
Salt added	Conc. of salt	10 ² × <i>k</i> ₂ l moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	
Manganese sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	7.207	
Cobalt sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	7.442	
Magnesium sulphate	.051 <i>M</i>	10.000	
Uranyl acetate	.050 <i>M</i>	8.921	
Sodium sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	7.547	
Ammonium acetate	.050 <i>M</i>	7.194	
Sodium acetate	.050 <i>M</i>	6.050	
Chromium sulphate	.052 <i>M</i>	9.515	
Aluminium sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	6.801	
Ammonium sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	9.219	

DISCUSSION

As reported earlier⁴ the reaction involves the formation of carbonium ion by a two electron transfer in the rate determining step.

The tables and figure I reveal that the rate differences are not due to changes in ionic strength but due to specific salt effects. The presence of specific salt influences has been observed in many ionic reactions. It has been observed by Indelli, Nolan Jr. and Amis⁵ that in the case of hydrolysis of potassium ethyl malonate the rate is affected by the concentration of cations but not by valence of the anions and therefore not by ionic strength effect. This observation is an extension of the observation made by Hoppe and Prue⁶, that multivalent and Thallous ions catalyse the hydrolysis of oxalate and the malonate esters and the alkali metal ions have a negative salt effect on reactions of adipate and sebacates. Even in inorganic reactions like persulphate and iodide ion reactions Indelli and Prue⁷ have observed that over a range of ionic strengths above 0.0034 ml^{-1} the effects are very specific, there is some correlation with the concentrations of ions of charge opposite to that of the reactants but none with ionic strength. Even in the case of bromate-iodide reaction salt effects do not depend strictly on ionic strength. Rather they are to a certain extent dependent on the concentration of the cation and an increase in ionic strength has, if any, an effect opposite to that predicted by Bronsted-Christiansen-Scatchard equation⁸.

Olson and Simonson⁹ while discussing the effect of addition of inert salts on the rates of ionic reactions asserted that for reaction between ions of like charge the effect is almost exclusively due to concentration and character of ions of charge opposite to that of the reactants and that the rate is not simply dependent on the ionic strength of solutions.

Thus in view of all the above evidences in well recognised ionic reactions which indicate the presence of specific salt effects and the absence of ionic strength effects, it is not surprising that in the reaction under consideration, we are observing specific salt influence, as this is only an anion-dipolar reaction. Tables I and II show that increase of cation concentration increases the rate. Figure I also reveals that the effect is just linear in the concentration range used. This is also clear from the increased rates with ammonium sulphate over ammonium acetate, as the concentration of ammonium ions is higher in the former case. Ion-dipolar reactions have been reported to have specific salt effects. Anantakrishnan and Anantaraman¹⁰ reported a primary salt effect on the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate. Long, McDevit and Dunkle also reported a salt effect on the acid catalysed hydrolysis of γ -butyrolactone. They explain that in equation

$$K_2 = K_2^0 \frac{f_A \cdot f_S}{f_x}$$

the addition of sodium chloride increases the activity coefficient of the lactone and that is responsible for the upward trend in the rate constant on the addition of sodium chloride.

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An attempt is made to correlate the ionic conductance of the cation and rate constants for some salts (Table III).

FIG-1

TABLE III

Acidity—8.1 <i>N</i> (H_2SO_4) Solvent Composition (% v/v) HOAc— H_2O 50–50		Substrate : Toluene Temp. 60°	
Salt added	Conc. of salt	$10^2 \times k_2$ l moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	λ_0
Ammonium sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	9.219	73.4
Magnesium sulphate	.051 <i>M</i>	10.000	53.06
Sodium sulphate	.050 <i>M</i>	7.547	50.11
Ammonium acetate	.050 <i>M</i>	7.194	73.4

The effect of the oxidisable ion like Mn^{++} might be rationalized also on the basis of its participation in the intermediate valence states of vanadium during the reaction causing acceleration. Organic bases also do not affect the rates (Table IV) much as found in the case of chromic acid oxidation of toluene and aldehydes^{11,12}. The effect appears to be normal.

TABLE IV

Acidity—8.1 <i>N</i> (H_2SO_4) Solvent Composition (% v/v) HOAc— H_2O 50–50		Substrate : Toluene Temp. 60°	
Base added		$10^2 \times k_2$ l moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	
Dipyridyl		6.305	
Orthophenanthroline		6.223	

If we consider that in these mixed solvent systems the added cations function by an effective reduction in the activity of water through the formation of a coordination sphere of water molecules, the availability of water for reaction in mixed solvent systems will be considerably reduced. When the availability of reactive content of water is decreased as this is a positive ion-dipolar reaction, the reaction rate increases which is the observed result by cation addition. Amis rationalized that there are two effects operating, polarization and electrostatic effect and these are responsible for the observed trend.

CONCLUSION

Finally it may be summarized as follows :

- (1) Sodium and ammonium acetates affect the reaction differently.
- (2) Magnesium, Manganese and Cobalt Sulphates affect the reaction differently.
- (3) Chromium and aluminium sulphates influence the rates much differently.

This confirms that the reaction is subject to specific salt influences as mentioned before.

The effect of uranyl acetate deserves mention. It has been observed by Indelli and Amis (loc cit.) that uranyl salt accelerated the rate abnormally in the reaction between bromate and iodide ions. The following equation was suggested for the abnormal acceleration.

The action of the uranyl ion was deemed to be specific.

Surprisingly the uranyl ion did not affect the reaction much. It can be said that uranyl ion just functioned like any other bivalent cation.

It seems however that more specific factors must be taken into consideration. In fact the relative efficiency of the cations can be different for various reactions between anions and even the order of efficiency can be reversed.

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